

CRITERIA AND INDICATORS FOR PROVIDING EMPLOYMENT AND IMPROVING THE WELL-BEING OF THE POPULATION IN RURAL AREAS

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Abstract: *In this article, lifestyle, work, social forms of its organization, forms of free time use, participation in political and social life, forms of meeting material and spiritual needs, norms and rules of people's behavior in everyday life are considered in this article.*

Keywords: *population, labor, political, social, material, spiritual, standard of living, unemployment.*

Introduction. Ensuring the employment of the population in the conditions of market relations is one of the important issues. Because the existence of the problem of unemployment is an integral feature of the market economy. Therefore, the main goal of studying the problem of unemployment is to develop measures related to expanding the country's production and improving the living standards of the population by increasing the employment of the population.

Consistently implemented reforms in our country, economic liberalization, modernization of society, and measures aimed at ensuring macroeconomic stability have led to deep structural changes in the country's economy. The main goal of the reforms and radical changes implemented in the years of independence is to continuously raise the standard of living of the country's population and raise it to the level of developed countries.

In the conditions of a socially oriented market economy, every individual who works effectively for the development of society, actively participates in social production and contributes to the creation of the gross domestic product, regardless of his gender, nationality, etc., can meet the reasonable needs of himself and his family it should be provided with a salary that will make it possible to live a comfortable life. In addition, every able-bodied person who wishes to participate in social production should have the opportunity to find a job that is suitable for him and his abilities and to freely settle in it without artificial obstacles. It is very important to look at labor resources as a valuable resource in the market economy and it is the main condition for the formation of a modern economy based on the human factor. At the present time, great attention is being paid to providing productive employment for purposeful utilization of labor resources in order to increase the welfare of the population. Economic problems such as effective use of labor resources, provision of productive jobs to the working population, rational use of natural resources are the main issues of modern economics and macroeconomic policy of all countries.

Based on the above points, we can emphasize that increasing the labor activity of the employed is not only encouraging them to work efficiently with the help of various factors and tools (salary, reward, etc.), but also creating the necessary conditions for such work. and attracting a workforce that has the potential to work effectively. In other words, one should never forget that only those who are able to work effectively, who have the capacity and opportunity to

work effectively can work effectively. Therefore, among all other factors of production in the enterprise, efficient use of labor force, sufficient development of the enterprise's activities,

The first- formation of the labor potential of the enterprise team and every worker in it, the intelligence, skills, knowledge, abilities embodied in it, and the hidden possibilities that can be used every time during the production process, but have not yet been realized, i.e., have not been expressed in the finished product, that is, the labor potential . There are two main ways to create a high labor potential in the enterprise: hiring qualified, knowledgeable, capable, hardworking, responsible people, that is, people with a high labor potential, and always taking care of the continuous improvement of the labor potential of the employees. In this case, it is necessary to conduct special tests of the candidate for employment, to study the description given to him from the previous workplace or by the educational institution, as well as the work biography. It is advisable to hire a candidate for a job first for a certain period (for example, 2 months, in some cases 4 or 6 months, with the condition of setting a trial period), and then permanent employment. This practice creates favorable opportunities for forming the enterprise team from personnel with high labor potential, reducing to a certain extent the dissatisfaction of personnel, which has a great negative impact on the enterprise's work results, and preventing accidental, low-responsibility employees from falling into the ranks of the labor team. In addition, great attention should be paid to continuously increasing the labor potential of the labor team formed in the enterprise. For this purpose, on the basis of training, retraining, upgrading the skills of working employees, arming them with modern knowledge,

The second- effective use of the labor potential formed in the enterprise, ensuring that this potential is expressed in the real quantity and quality of goods and services produced in the enterprise, turning the labor potential embodied in the labor force into the results of labor. The solution to this problem requires the enterprise administration and economic service specialists to fully realize the labor potential formed in each employee, to fully mobilize the knowledge and skills, experience and opportunities embodied in it, to perform the assigned functional tasks and tasks diligently, responsibly and within the specified period. to be materially interested in the final results of the enterprise's activity, to ensure active participation in the social and economic development of the enterprise, requires finding effective methods and applying them in practice. It should not be forgotten that the role and importance of this factor in achieving the final results set before the enterprise in the process of solving the problems of effective use of the labor potential of the employed employees for the benefit of the enterprise is incomparable. The reason is that if a high labor potential is formed in the enterprise, but it is not used properly for the interests and development of the enterprise, then such potential will not be of any benefit to the enterprise. It is like a candle standing inside a supposedly dark house, but not lit: the candle lights up the house only if it is lit, otherwise such a candle is useless in solving the problem of lighting a dark house. It should not be forgotten that the role and importance of this factor in achieving the final results set before the enterprise in the process of solving the problems of effective use of the labor potential of the employed employees for the benefit of the enterprise is incomparable. The reason is that if a high labor potential is formed in the enterprise, but it is not used properly for the interests and development of the enterprise, then such potential will not be of any benefit to the enterprise. It is like a candle standing inside a supposedly dark house, but not lit: the candle lights up the house only if it is lit, otherwise such a candle is useless in solving the problem of lighting a dark house. It should not be forgotten that the role and importance of

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Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process

Analysis and results. For this reason, it is correct to say that not ensuring the employment of the population, but ensuring its productive employment is a specific urgent task of today. To create an opportunity for every citizen to study for a specific profession at the expense of the state. Doubling the scope of vocational training, training a total of 1 million unemployed citizens and increasing the participation of non-state educational institutions to 30% in this process" an effective solution to the problem of unemployment will be found.

In the conditions of globalization, the higher the internal competitiveness of all branches and sectors of the national economy of a particular country in the world market, especially in the world market, the higher the possibilities of solving the actual problems of population employment in that country. Many economists have different opinions about the socio-economic importance of employment, its role as an important factor in increasing the income and standard of living of the population, and the close relationship between employment and material well-being of people. As an example, we can cite the following. At that time, the great economist A. Smith in his well-known work "Research on the nature and causes of the wealth of nations" emphasized that there is an inextricable connection between employment and the material well-being of the population. Dj.M.

If our main goal in the near and long future is to dramatically increase the welfare of the population and bring it to the level of developed countries, it is necessary to achieve our goals based on this strategy. If the society achieves the full realization and use of the labor potential of the working population, leaving no room for waste, this indicator will also be high.

One of the unique aspects of the national economy of Uzbekistan is that a significant part of the labor resources is located in rural areas due to objective and subjective reasons.

However, the level of utilization of labor resources in rural areas is low. The macro-economic policy aimed at the faster development of small and private entrepreneurship in rural areas, ensuring employment of the population and increasing its material well-being based on the organization of processing of agricultural products does not give great positive results for a number of reasons.

The main indicator describing the well-being of the population is the standard of living of the population. The concept of the standard of living of the population can be defined as the level of provision of material and spiritual benefits necessary for their living and the satisfaction of people's needs with these benefits.

The system of indicators of the standard of living of the population recommended by the UN includes the following groups:

Birth and death rates and other demographic indicators.

Sanitary conditions of living.

Consumption of food products.

Accommodation conditions.

Education and culture.

Working and employment conditions.

Incomes and expenses of the population.

Cost of living and consumer prices.

Vehicles.

Organization of recreation.

Social security.

Human freedom.

In addition to these basic indicators, some more informational indicators are distinguished: GDP per capita, national income per capita, consumption volume per capita, etc.

The set of goods necessary for human life activities includes such diverse needs as working conditions, education, health, food and housing quality. The level of satisfaction of people's needs depends on the level of individual and family income of society members. Standard of living at country level (for the entire population) and at the stratified micro level (for a particular group of the population). The first approach makes it possible to determine the standard of living of the population in different countries according to the gross domestic product per capita and make a comparative analysis.

Comparison of the dynamics of income distribution by population groups is carried out on the basis of the consumer budget. There are several types of consumer budgets: average family budget, high income budget, minimum income budget, pensioners and other social groups budget. The lower limit of well-being can be defined by the limit of family income, below which the reproduction of the labor force cannot be ensured. This level comes out as the minimum level of material security or subsistence level (the beginning of poverty).

In the conditions of the market economy, the average income is determined by the income of the so-called "middle class". Such a group's consumer basket includes a house, a car, a yard, modern home furnishings, the opportunity to go for a walk and educate their children, securities, and zebu jewelry.

The market economy requires the existence of a high-income or "rich" layer of the population in other words, they include a very small amount of the population that is able to purchase high-quality goods and services.

The standard of living is closely related to people's lifestyle. Lifestyle is a socio-economic category that reflects the type and methods of life activity of people (society, social class, individual) in the national and world community. Lifestyle covers various aspects of human life activities, namely:

- labor, social forms of its organization;
- forms of life and free time use;
- participation in political and social life;
- forms of meeting material and spiritual needs;
- norms and rules of behavior of people in everyday life.

The number of people employed in the national economy and their share in the total population of the country is the most important macroeconomic indicator and has a great positive impact on the well-being of the population. We suggest using the following formula to express this relationship:

$$TD = \frac{BA \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n MY}{YA - BA}$$

TD - standard of living of the population

BA is the number of people employed in the economy

$\sum_{i=1}^n MY$ - the value created by those employed in the economy in a certain time unit (labor productivity)

UA - total population

The standard of living of the population of the country depends on the number of people employed in the economy and the value created by each worker in a certain unit of time, that is, directly proportional to labor productivity and inversely proportional to the number of people who do not participate in social production for certain reasons or by their own will.

Ensuring the employment of the population in the conditions of Samarkand region has become one of the most important problems of socio-economic development. The formation of labor resources and their use in rural areas have their own characteristics. They are related to the demographic situation in the villages, the limited opportunities of the rural population in choosing the employment sector and employment, the seasonality of agricultural production and a number of other factors.

One of the unique aspects of the economy of Samarkand region is that a significant part of the labor resources is located in rural areas. In addition, the number of people employed in agriculture occupies a large share in the total number of people employed in the economy. Currently, 63.0% of the labor resources of Samarkand region live in rural areas. The largest population in our republic 3947.7 thousand people. In order to increase the level of economic potential in the region where he lives, finding ways to improve the use of labor resources in rural areas is one of the important tasks of the current economic policy.

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